

These experiments showed a high extent of protein import as measured by inaccessibility to thermolysin digestion. We conclude that the cDNA from *N. pseudonarcissus* codes for a functional phytoene synthase and thus is suitable for rice transformation.

The cDNA was subcloned under the control of the CaMV35S promoter and glutelin promoter (Burkhardt et al 1996, Potrykus et al 1996). We examined the resulting transformants for phytoene synthase expression. First, reverse-transcriptase polymerase chain reaction was established to detect mRNA of the introduced transgenes in rice endosperm. The results revealed the presence of specific

mRNA, which was absent in endosperm of control plants. Second, using homologous anti-phytoene synthase antibodies, phytoene synthase was detected in transformed endosperm, whereas no signal was obtained in the control plants. Third, using RP-HPLC, the phytoene content was determined in mature rice seeds deprived of the embryo. Phytoene content was usually below detection limit in the controls: in some cases, however, insignificantly low amounts probably derived from seed coat were present.

In contrast, high amounts of phytoene found in seeds of some transformants allowed clear UV/VIS spectra-proving identity to be obtained. Constructs under glutelin promoter control were successful in

phytoene formation. The best line obtained so far showed a phytoene content of 1 μmol per gram (after quantification by calibrated integration on HPLC and use of a molar extinction coefficient of $68,125 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). This corresponds to 545 μg phytoene per gram, which is safely within the nutritionally useful range (Burkhardt et al 1996).

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Pest resistance—diseases

Screening of Basmati rice genotypes against blast

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Blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* Sacc.= *Magnaporthe grisea* (Hebert) Barr., is a devastating disease of scented, tall varieties in Haryana. We screened 175 rice genotypes in station and coordinated trials at the Rice Research Station in Kaul.

For leaf blast screening in the Uniform Blast Screening Nursery, we alternated each test genotype with susceptible variety Taraori Basmati on all sides during the 1993 kharif (dry season). For neck blast screening, 1-mo-old seedlings of test entries were transplanted in two 5-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. One line of Taraori Basmati was planted between each test entry to ensure maximum disease development. We recorded leaf blast incidence during the last week of September when the disease was at its peak. Tillers of 25 randomly selected hills of each test entry were examined for neck blast 1 wk before harvest. We scored the disease severity using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1988). Genotypes showing

Basmati rice genotypes showing resistance to blast. Haryana, India, 1993 and 1994 kharifs.

Leaf blast	Neck blast	Both leaf and neck blast
HKR86-416	HKR90-403	HKR90-403
HKR90-403	HKR90-404	HKR91-405
HKR90-407	HKR91-405	
HKR90-410	HKR91-431	
HKR91-401	RP3121-14-10-2	
HKR91-402	RP3138-60-91-0-6	
HKR91-404	RP3238-38-15-7-1	
HKR91-405	RPST328	
HKR91-408	NDR637-90	
HKR91-413	UPR-BS-92-5	
HKR91-424		
HKR91-427		
HKR91-456		
HKR91-459		
HKR91-460		
HKR91-467		
HKR92-405		
HKR92-409		
HKR239		

resistance to leaf or neck blast were retested during 1994 kharif to confirm their reaction to the disease.

We found 19 genotypes resistant to leaf blast and 10 genotypes to neck blast during both years (see table). Only genotypes HKR90-403 and HKR91-405 showed resistance to both leaf and neck blast. Besides blast, three genotypes (HKR86-416, HKR90-404, and HKR92-405) also exhibited resistance to stem rot. ■

Resistance spectrum, race specificity, and expression of the *Xa21* gene family

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The rice gene *Xa21* confers resistance to the bacterial pathogen *Xanthomonas oryzae* (*Xoo*) (Ikeda et al 1990, Ronald et al 1992). The *Xa21* locus consists of a small multigene family, and transgenic lines (T_0) expressing a single member of the *Xa21* gene family confer resistance to *Xoo* race 6 (Song et al 1996). Unlike all other cloned plant disease resistance genes, the deduced amino acid sequence of *Xa21* encodes a glycosylated leucine-rich repeat (LRR) extracellular domain, a single-pass transmembrane domain, and a serine threonine kinase intracellular domain. The sequence of the predicted protein of *Xa21* strongly suggests its role in cell-surface recognition of a pathogen ligand and subsequent activation of an intracellular defense response.

To determine the resistance spectrum of cloned resistance gene *Xa21*, we tested 300 T_1 progeny from the transgenic line 106-17 containing *Xa21* for *Xoo* resistance.

Inoculation results indicate that adding a single gene (*Xa21*) is sufficient to confer resistance to all seven Philippine races of *Xoo* and 20 isolates from China, Colombia, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Nepal, and Thailand. Resistance to *Xoo* strains of Philippine races 1 through 6 cosegregated with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) profile of the *Xa21* transgene in a 3:1 ratio. Southern blot analysis confirmed the PCR results, indicating that a single member of the *Xa21* multigene family can confer resistance to diverse strains isolated from seven countries.

The *Xa21* gene family contains eight members, all located at the *Xa21* locus. Each member contains an LRR motif.

Differences in the LRR domain of the family may play a role in the specificity of pathogen recognition. To test this idea, we generated transgenic plants carrying subclones from other members of the *Xa21* gene family. The resistance of these lines to the six *Xoo* races has been determined. Preliminary screening showed that at least one copy (copy D) confers partial resistance to races 1 and 6 in transgenic plants.

To analyze the expression of the *Xa21* gene family, we made a cDNA library from the resistant line infected with *Xoo*. We identified 17 cDNAs hybridizing with LRR or/and kinase domains. Sequencing results indicate that at least four copies of the gene family are expressed.

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A bacterial blight-resistant, wide-compatible indica line

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In China, scientists started to develop innovative elite lines with genes for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (*Xoo*) in the early 1980s. Scientists are now using wide compatibility as an approach to develop indica/japonica hybrid rice through pyramiding genes for wide compatibility, disease resistance, and agronomically important characters.

We determined resistance to BB by evaluating lesion length 20 d after inoculation (9×10^8 cells ml⁻¹ concentration) using the clipping method at booting stage. We used 10 *Xoo* isolates (provided by the Plant Protection Department, Nanjing Agricultural University) of major pathotypes I through VII from different provinces in China: OS14 (I) (Liaoning),

KS-6-6 (II) (Jiangsu), HB84-17 (II) (Heibe), OS105 (II) (Guangdong), FJ856 (III) (Fujian), ZHE173 (IV) (Zhejiang), AH023 (IV) (Anfei), GD1358 (V) (Guangdong), GX325 (V) (Guangxi), and JS49-6 (VII) (Hunan).

We evaluated wide compatibility using spikelet fertility from testcrosses to both typical indica and japonica cultivars. Mean fertility of unbagged F₁ plants was assessed at maturity. Spikelet fertility of up to 70% was normal and compatible.

85-21416 is a promising indica line developed from a 1978 cross between Taichung Native 1, a susceptible and noncompatible indica cultivar from Taiwan, China, and DZ78, a highly resistant, tall indica from Bangladesh. 85-21416 has strong resistance to BB and is extremely compatible in intersubspecific crosses. We grew F₃ lines of this cross combination in early spring of 1980. We then selected individuals each year through artificial inoculation evaluation. By 1985, 85-21416 along with other advanced lines (F₇₋₈) were selected for stable resistance and other

characters. 85-21416 was used in 1988 as a resistance donor in intersubspecific genetic studies.

The shorter lesion lengths of 85-21416 confirmed its stable BB resistance (Table 1). A recessive gene allelic to *xa5* (data not shown) controls the resistance. 85-21416 may have inherited the resistance

Table 2. F₁ spikelet fertilities of 85-21416 crossed with various tester varieties.^a

Cross combination ^b	Mean	Plants (no.)
Balilla/85-21416	87.3 ± 3.58	15
Aikihikari/85-21416	91.7 ± 3.20	14
85-21416/IR36	87.9 ± 5.04	6
02428/85-21416	79.4 ± 5.28	12
Ketan Nangka/ 85-21416	62.5 ± 1.41	18
85-21416/CPSL017	68.4 ± 1.73	18
85-21416 (I)	80.6 ± 5.31	14
Balilla (J)	67.9 ± 4.86	12
Aikihikari (J)	89.3 ± 3.51	10
02428 (J)	71.4 ± 7.06	10
IR36 (I)	92.9 ± 1.05	15
CPSL017 (I)	82.6 ± 3.00	10

^aData were collected in 1992, except those for 85-21416/IR36 and IR36, which were collected in Sep 1995. ^bI = indica, J = japonica.

Table 1. Reactions of 85-21416 to bacterial blight isolates compared with Nanjing 11, DV85, and IRBB7.

Line/variety	Gene	Isolates										Evaluation criterion	Year
		OS14	HB84-17	KS-6-6	OS105	FJ856	ZHE173	AH023	GD1358	GX325	JS94-6		
85-21416	<i>xa5(t)</i>	1.7	1.4	1.8	0.8	1.1	1.1	1.5	3.9	1.6	0.6	Lesion length (cm)	1994
DV85	<i>xa5, Xa7</i>	1.2	1.1	1.2	1.5	1.1	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.6	0.9	Lesion length (cm)	1994
IRBB117	<i>Xa7</i>	-	3.0	-	-	-	3.0	-	5.0	-	3.0	Leaf area necrotized (%)	1995
Nanjing 11	None	19.8	26.1	25.8	20.6	13.1	19.8	23.7	9.7	25.6	10.2	Lesion length (cm)	1994